

DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

A survey of ascorbic acid producers and other trade sources associated with the business last week turned up more indications that the pressure on that compound is easing. At the end of 1971, the so-called "gray market" price of vitamin C declined from a reported level of about \$11 to a \$7 or \$8 a kilo (Chem Marketing 2/7/72, page 17). Last week virtually all trade sources

said that the gray market price continues to decline in the direction of what one producer called a "realistic" level.

List prices have been in the range of \$4 to \$5 a kilo, depending on quantity, for some time now.

Nevertheless, producers do not say that they have developed any substantial inventories of spot material. "It isn't a free market," one of them says.

Apart from the reported decline of the gray market (both as to size and as to the prices prevailing in it), the clearest evidence of loosening in ascorbic's position is to be seen in import figures.

Ascorbic entires during the first five months of 1972 totaled some 2.3 million pounds. In January-May 1971, they amounted to 2.8 million pounds. The reduction amounts to about 16 percent.

On the basis of this decline, one US producer theorizes that "either US demand has tapered off slightly, or that overseas producers can sell at higher prices in the European and Far East markets."

It's most likely, he adds, that both of these things are happening. Virtually all market observers said last week that they believed demand here has weakened. Trade sources did not confirm whether there has been any important new movement of ascorbic in the Far East and European markets.

Demand Unsustainable

There is no doubt that all of these observers would agree with the proposition asserted by one of them, that nothing could have sustained the enormous demand for ascorbic stimulated by Linus Pauling's widely publicized assertions as to its therapeutic qualities.

They also agreed that the traditional ascorbic food fortification and pharmaceutical—are holding up well.

Figures on domestic production for 1972 to date aren't available. In April and March, US manufacturers made a total of about 2.8 million pounds, according to the Tariff Commission, as opposed to 2.3 million in March-April 1971—for a gain of about 16 percent.

Last week the producers declined to speculate on whether or not production in the unreported months followed a similar pattern, although one of them said his own output is unchanged.

A spokesman for Roche Chemical Division of Hoffman-LaRoche here said his company operated at capacity last year, and he intimated that it continues to do so.

In response to a question on progress at the company's big new ascorbic plant, he said that Roche "still expects to be able to meet customers' demand by the beginning" of 1973, although he declined to add any specifics on the plant beyond those already published.

Roche's plant is expected to come on stream during the third or fourth quarter of 1972, according to a report emanating from the company last Winter (Chem Marketing, 2/7/72, page 17). The report said capacity would be in the neighborhood of 10 million kilos a year.

If the report is accurate, the new capacity would be a very significant addition. In the US, for example, production of ascorbic acid amounted to 11.7 million pounds in all of 1971, or about half the potential Roche says its new plant will have.

Brucine—Output and consumption of brucine continues to decline. An FDA source in Washington explained that brucine, like many alkaloids, is highly toxic in large dosage, and while it is used in very small concentration as a denaturant for SD-40 alcohol and special formulas for hairsprays, industry is possibly looking to other alternatives as a use for denaturing alcohol.

The leveling off of output and consumption has presented a sharp turnaround situation from the spate of heavy buying of brucine during 1970, when Israel began processing raw material from India, causing an increase in US consumption.

Whereas prices five to six years ago had gone as high as \$5 per ounce for brucine, Israeli production led to a steady

THE WEEK'S PRICE CHANGES

Ending July 14, 1972

ADVANCED
Silver cyanide, 80% Ag., 6.2c. per oz.
Silver nitrate, ACS, 5c. per oz.

REDUCED
None

COMPARATIVE PRICE INDEXES (100=1959 average)

Last Week	Prev. Week	Last Month	July 16, 1971
80.77	80.76	80.74	80.12

For Current Prices See Page 30

decline in prices, and accordingly prices from other sources dropped. Brucine inventories, in turn, were raised to unusually high levels, and by 1971, inventories were far ahead of demand.

In 1970, US buyers purchased 600,000 ounces of brucine, exceeding by 20 percent the yearly figure of 500,000 ounces for the 1960 to 1971 period.

The over-supply has yielded a steady decline in prices for brucine, and last week, sources report that prices continue dropping. NF-sulfate in 25,000 lots, which had been selling for about 75c. an ounce, has dropped by 6c. It's quoted now at about 69c.

Brucine alkaloid in 25,000-lot quantities has also dropped by 6c. according to last week's reports, and is now offered at 79c., against former listings of 85c. One source reported even lower prices, quoting 65c. per ounce for NF sulfate and 70c. to 75c. for brucine alkaloid.

Israeli Role Questioned

Nevertheless, several US importers contacted deny that declining prices may have anything to do with a decline in output or demand. One agent for brucine shipped from Israel said that "reduced figures in imports are more apparent than real."

Business in brucine is done in the form of large contracts with Israel, he asserted, rather than on a spot basis, as with India. Consequently, added another source, offers are for future and not immediate orders.

These comments were especially puzzling, in light of current trade rumors that India's nux vomica, from which brucine is manufactured, is in short supply, and also in light of rumors that Israel may drop exports of several alkaloids, including brucine.

Moreover, annual figures on exports from Israel, where the raw material undergoes processing, especially points to a possible waning of brucine consumption. In 1971, Israeli exports had declined 32 percent from 1968, with 157,000 ounces exported to US buyers. This year, the January to April figures report only 32,000 ounces from Israel, against 248,648 ounces from India.

Listed in the Merck Index as a "highly toxic alkaloid resembling strychnine," brucine has traditionally been used in the US for denaturing alcohol, particularly in conjunction with aerosol hairsprays and related cosmetic applications, reported by one source to account for about 50% of brucine consumption.

Gelatin—Researchers at Eastman Kodak Co.'s industrial laboratory at Rochester, N.Y., have come up with "a promising new scientific application" for gelatin, as a standard reference material for checking trace quantities of mercury and, possibly, other metals.

The researchers, Don H. Anderson, J. J. Murphy and W. W. White, report that other reference media, such as frozen fish, dried leaves, flour and fishmeal are subject to bacterial decomposition and other kinds of decomposition.

The Kodak gelatin reference samples reportedly remained stable for more than a year. Gelatin is said to be an ideal carrier, because it is similar to many of the

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Drug Disclosures Proposals Rapped Again by PMA

Pharmaceutical Manufacturers Association is pressing Food & Drug Administration to ease up on its plans to throw open to public scrutiny much of the drug data in heretofore confidential files. Under FDA's proposed regulations, the question of whether New Drug Application (NDA) data could be disclosed would depend mainly on the specific drug's regulatory status. Information subject to disclosure would include that for "old drugs" not

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Report From Europe

Benzene Futures a Hot Topic As ICI Studies Possibilities, Mulls Idea with Bank, Broker

